

INTERNATIONAL INSTITUTE OF RURAL RECONSTRUCTION

A large, mature tree with a thick trunk and dense green foliage is the central focus. The tree is heavily laden with clusters of small, light pink flowers. The background shows a clear blue sky and other trees in a park-like setting.

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PUBLICATIONS
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PUBLICATIONS
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PHILIPPINES

GARNERING NATURE FRIENDLY AGRICULTURE PRACTICES: 1990 TO 2020

Authors: Gonsalves, J.

Date: 2021-05-07

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/113673>

INFORMATION RESOURCES ON GARDENING, NUTRITION AND NUTRITION-SENSITIVE AGRICULTURE (NUTRITION COMPENDIUM)

Authors: Oro, E.M., Baguilat, I., Anunciado, M. S., Itliong, K., Valdemoro, C., Calica, M., de Castro, R., Barbon, W., Thy, O., Soksophors, Y., Dominguez, D., Soria, G., Capanzana, M., Agdeppa, I., & Gonsalves, J.

Date: 2020-4

Link: <http://bit.ly/2Lkw3wi>

INFORMATION RESOURCES FOR ACTION RESEARCHERS/PRACTITIONERS IN CLIMATE RESILIENT AGRICULTURE

Authors: Gonsalves J, Dominguez D, Soria G, Vidallo R, Bayot R, Barbon W, Soksophors Y, Bernardo EB, Amutan C.

Date: 2020-02

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/107971>

AGROBIODIVERSITY, SCHOOL GARDENS AND HEALTHY DIETS: PROMOTING BIODIVERSITY, FOOD AND SUSTAINABLE NUTRITION

Authors: Hunter, D.; Monville-Oro, E.; Burgos, B.; Rogel, C.N.; Calub, B.; Gonsalves, J.; Lauridsen, N.O.

Date: 2020

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/107465>

SCHOOL GARDENS: MULTIPLE FUNCTIONS AND MULTIPLE OUTCOMES

Authors: Gonsalves, J.; Hunter, D.; Lauridsen, N

Date: 2020

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/110525>

TOWARDS CLIMATE RESILIENCE IN AGRICULTURE FOR SOUTHEAST ASIA: AN OVERVIEW FOR DECISION-MAKERS

Authors: Gonsalves J; Campilan D; Smith G; Bui VL; Jimenez FM (Eds.).

Date: 2015

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/71100>

RECIPE BOOK FOR COMPLEMENTARY FEEDING

Author: International Institute of Rural
Reconstruction

Date: 2019-11-29

Link: <https://bit.ly/3GF11Hk>

HOME GARDENING BOOKLET

Author: International Institute of Rural
Reconstruction, Food and Nutrition
Research Institute, Department of
Education

Date: 2019-12-13

Link: <https://bit.ly/2ZDreVH>

DEVELOPED RECIPES USING INDIGENOUS VEGETABLES

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction, Food and Nutrition Research Institute, Department of Education

Date: 2013-06

Link: <https://bit.ly/3iitouF>

IRON RICH RECIPES

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction, Food and Nutrition Research Institute, Department of Education

Date: 2017-10-06

Link: <https://bit.ly/3bBOXIF>

CO-BENEFITS FROM FAMILY FARMS

Authors: Valerio, A.T., Onuh, W.O., and Dalusag, J.B.

Date: 2021-02

Link: <http://bit.ly/3bIKXWs>

VIABILITY OF FAMILY FARMING: BRIEF FOR DECISION MAKERS

Authors: Valerio, A.T., Onuh, W.O., and Dalusag, J.B.

Date: 2021

Link: <http://bit.ly/3sHDAWF>

CSA OPTIONS IMPLEMENTED AND EVALUATED ACROSS THE CCAFS CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGES AR4D SITES: 2019 GLOBAL INVENTORY

Authors: Bonilla-Findji, Osana; Martinez, Jesus David; Ortega, Luis Alfonso; Paz, Liliana; Lopez, Claudia; Alvarez, Osman; Ouédraogo, Mathieu; Recha, John; Vidallo, Rene

Date: 2020-12-21

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/111515>

8 Hakbang sa Pagtatatag ng Climate-Smart na Pook (CSP)

Nang 2015, sinimula ng CGIAR Research Program on Climate Change, Agriculture and Food Security (CRP) ang pagtatatag ng mga Climate-Smart na Pook o CSP (Climate-Smart Village) sa Timog Silangang Asya, upang magbigay maging komunidad na matatag sa nagbabagong klima (climate risk) sa lugar kung saan itatayo ang CSP.

Ang CSP ay isang platapormang nihalalukan ng maraming aktor. Ito ay ginagamit nito ang mga nabuong kaalaman at institusyonal na opsiyon para sa climate change adaptation at mitigation sa agrikultura. Dahil binibigyang-diin ng CSP ang konteksto, mga proseso, at mga resulta (outcomes), nagpapalaganap nang laki ang makabagong paraan upang mapatupad ang CSP sa mga kanyunon at lugar na mga lugar.

1. Ipaliwanag ang layunin at sakop ng itatayang CSP
2. Tukuyin ang mga panganib na dala ng nagbabagong klima (climate risk) sa lugar kung saan itatayo ang CSP
3. Maghanap ng potensiyal na CSP sa isang maliit ng lapad
4. Konsultahin ang mga kalahok sa pagtatayo ng mga CSP
5. Surin ang mga pinagpipiliang CSA
6. Bumuo ng portfolio
7. Palawigin ang saklaw ng itatayang CSP
8. Subaybayan at surin ang pagtanggap sa CSP at ang mga lalabas na resulta sa pagtatatag nito

8 HAKBANG SA PAGTATATAG NG CLIMATE-SMART NA POOK (CSP)

Authors: Sebastian, Leocadio S.; Gonsalves, Julian; Bernardo, Eisen Bernard

Date: 2020-07-27

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/108882>

8 Bước hướng dẫn thành lập Làng Nông Thuận Thiên (CSV)

Được giới thiệu vào năm 2015 bởi Chương trình Nghiên cứu của CGIAR về biến đổi khí hậu, Nông nghiệp và An ninh Lương thực (CRP), Làng Nông Thuận Thiên (CSV) được thành lập nhằm xây dựng các mô hình cộng đồng thích ứng với biến đổi khí hậu và thực hiện thị trường Nông nghiệp thông minh thích ứng với biến đổi khí hậu (CSA). CRP ở Đông Nam Á đã thành lập bảy CSV trong khu vực, bao gồm thôn Mã thôn Mỹ Lợi và xã Tân Hội tại Việt Nam, thôn Phnom và Kvang tại Lào, thôn Rohal Suong ở Campuchia, và thôn Guinayangan ở Philippines.

CSV là một nền tảng đa ngành để thử nghiệm các giải pháp công nghệ và thể chế thích ứng và giảm thiểu biến đổi khí hậu trong nông nghiệp. Làm nổi bật bối cảnh, quy trình và kết quả, bản tóm tắt CSV được chứng minh là một cách tiếp cận sáng tạo trong việc lồng ghép CSA vào phát triển nông nghiệp thông minh và cảnh quan xung quanh.

1. Xác định mục đích và phạm vi của các CSV đang được thành lập
2. Xác định rủi ro khí hậu tại các khu vực mục tiêu
3. Chọn một cảnh quan cụ thể để thành lập CSV
4. Tham vấn các bên liên quan
5. Đánh giá các giải pháp CSA
6. Phát triển danh mục
7. Nhân rộng mô hình
8. Theo dõi, giám sát thực hiện và đánh giá kết quả

8 BƯỚC HƯỚNG DẪN THÀNH LẬP LÀNG NÔNG THUẬN THIÊN (CSV) (Vietnamese version)

Authors: Sebastian, Leocadio S.; Gonsalves, Julian; Bernardo, Eisen Bernard

Date: 2019-12-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/108348>

Climate Smart Agriculture: Models for Empowering Women Livestock Producers

2015 DANIEL TOMLIN

BRIEF

CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURE: MODELS FOR EMPOWERING WOMEN LIVESTOCK PRODUCERS

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2019-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/102278>

RESILIENCE BUILDING AND CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION FOR COASTAL COMMUNITIES (MODEL BUILDING FOR SMALL MUNICIPALITIES IN THE PHILIPPINES)

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2019-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/102277>

AGROFORESTRY FOR A CHANGING CLIMATE

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2019-01

Type: Brief

Link 1: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/102276>

Link 2: <https://bit.ly/3uCkoLD> (with correction)

IMPROVING FOOD AND NUTRITION SECURITY IN THE PHILIPPINES THROUGH SCHOOL INTERVENTION

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-05

Link: <https://bit.ly/3bypPm1>

LIGHTHOUSE SCHOOLS: DECENTRALIZED PLATFORMS FOR OUTSCALING SCHOOL NUTRITION INTERVENTION

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-05-03

Link: <https://bit.ly/3q1lINc>

LEVERAGING THE NUTRITIONAL CONTRIBUTIONS OF AGRICULTURE

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction, International Development Research Centre

Date: 2017-11-07

Link: <http://bit.ly/3qNYWjx>

BUILDING COMMUNITY-BASED MODELS FOR CLIMATE RESILIENT AGRICULTURE AND FISHERIES ACROSS LANDSCAPES WITHIN THE MUNICIPALITY OF IVISAN, CAPIZ

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2017-09-21

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/89040>

TOWARDS A PORTFOLIO OF CLIMATE RESILIENT TECHNOLOGICAL OPTIONS: COMMUNITY LEVEL PARTICIPATORY ADAPTIVE RESEARCH

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2017-09-21

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/89041>

CROP MUSEUMS IN SCHOOLS: CONSERVING AGROBIODIVERSITY OF NUTRITIONAL IMPORTANCE

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2017-03

Link: <https://bit.ly/3mApZ2p>

BIO-INTENSIVE GARDENS (BIG): A CLIMATE & NUTRITION SMART AGRICULTURE APPROACH

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2017-02

Link: <https://bit.ly/3bAEIEg>

SMALL WATERSHEDS AND LANDSCAPES: ENGAGING LOCAL STAKEHOLDERS IN CONSERVATION

Authors: International Institute of Rural
Reconstruction, Philippine Tropical
Forest Conservation Foundation, Inc.

Date: 2017-06

Link: <http://bit.ly/39VAaas>

DEVELOPING SCALABLE APPROACHES FOR COMMUNITY-BASED ADAPTATION: A BRIEF

Author: International Institute of Rural
Reconstruction

Date: 2016-11

Link: <https://bit.ly/35SQyY4>

PRACTICAL APPROACHES TO INTEGRATING RESILIENCE ELEMENTS IN DISASTER RECOVERY: BRIEF

Authors: International Institute of Rural
Reconstruction, Zoological Society of
London – Philippines, The Local
Government Unit of Ivisan, Capiz, The
American Jewish Joint Distribution
Committee, The Jewish Federations of
North America

Date: 2015-06

Link: <http://bit.ly/2MoQKOe>

Info Note

Nurturing a gender-responsive approach to climate-smart agriculture in Guinayangan, Quezon

Magnolia Rosimo, Julian Gonsalves, and Francis Villavicencio
eprints@iirr.org

Key messages

- Context-based farming systems in Guinayangan, Quezon offer special opportunities for an agronomy that can coordinate existing family-based, resource-intensive, and labor-intensive systems to improve the livelihoods and resilience of women and children and reduce the risk of malnutrition and malnutrition.
- Gender-based inequalities within context-based farming systems can be addressed through agronomy-based, context-specific agricultural practices that include small business, fish, and other and local crops as underlying crops.
- Nurturing Climate-Smart Villages, spread across the municipality of Guinayangan, Quezon, can provide a gender-responsive approach to climate-smart agriculture based on agronomy interventions and gender services.

An overview of gender and climate: What the literature tells us

Growing evidence suggests that climate change affects men and women differently, especially in developing countries, because of cultural norms and inequalities in the distribution of risks, resources and processes (Patterson, R., 2012). Climate change exacerbates inequalities because the poor are less able to bounce back from shocks and climate hazards and are more likely to experience poverty (Carter, J.B., Naidu, G., 2011). Gender, the complex relationships and roles that exist between men and women (Escobar et al., 2008). Poor rural women in developing countries are generally considered to be the most vulnerable to climate change (Global Gender Climate Alliance, 2015; Chant et al., 2010; 2008). Many observed free-market pathways that render women more vulnerable to climate change than men. There are biological and physiological differences, pre-

existing social norms and role behavior, and exacerbated and new forms of gender discrimination (Patterson, 2014; 2012; Rosimo et al., eprints@iirr.org, 2015). 2015) argue that "vulnerability is dynamic, locally specific and embedded along social, gender and economic lines." Because of these differences in vulnerabilities and capacities, women and men farmers in developing countries have different abilities to adapt to climate change (Kajane et al., 2015). For example, resource-poor farmers, due to lack of capital and limited farm inputs, possess fewer options for the adoption of conservation agriculture or climate change adaptation strategies (Dobson et al., 2010; 2012). Other studies have found that financial and resource constraints as well as lower levels of access to information and extension services can prevent women from implementing adaptive practices (Lal et al., 2015; Tal et al., 2014; Trnka et al., 2014). Climate variability and weather-related shocks affect women and men in different ways (Lal et al., 2015; Kropf et al., 2016). Women and men are changing their cropping practices in response to climate variability, with different impacts on access to and control of the income, as well as their respective livelihoods (Lal et al., 2015; Nelson & Steiner, 2009).

Empowering women in agriculture

Climate, agriculture remains one of the most important areas of women's work. With more than a third of agricultural households in agricultural households (around 40% of the agricultural labor force in developing countries (FAO, 2011). Less than 20% of agricultural households worldwide are women (FAO, 2010). Women's agricultural activities are concentrated in higher gender gaps in vulnerabilities, access to resources and productivity (FAO, 2011; Pineda et al., 2010; Chant and Paredes, 2012). Substantiated gender gaps in access and control continue to exist regarding an key resource

NURTURING A GENDER-RESPONSIVE APPROACH TO CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE IN GUINAYANGAN, QUEZON

Authors: Rosimo M, Gonsalves J, Villavicencio F.

Date: 2021-10

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/115800>

BRIEF

Fostering local adaptation platforms for agriculture: How context-specific climate-smart villages (CSVs) can relate to local adaptation efforts

Rene Vidallo, Bayot Bayot, Magnolia Rosimo, Emilita Monville-Oro, Julian Gonsalves, Alicia Sags, Leocadio Sebastian, U-Nichols, Manalo, Perla Baltazar
January 2020

Climate Resilience in Agriculture: How context-specific climate-smart villages (CSVs) could help

Climate change is expected to adversely affect lives, livelihoods, nutrition, and food security in the future. Free and fair trade, we can do a lot to reduce the impacts of climate change, build resilience to our food systems, ensure food safety, reduce risks and vulnerabilities of farming communities, and protect agriculture and smallholder farmers.

Adapting to climate change requires adjusting agricultural practices to meet changing and more difficult environmental conditions. Traditional and newly introduced practices can help farmers cope with current variability and future climate risks. Climate-smart agriculture (CSA) through Resilient Agriculture (CSA) is one way of helping farmers prepare for the future.

Climate change affects different communities in different ways. Adaptation efforts must therefore be localized and context-specific. Various studies have already shown that smallholder farmers are most vulnerable to adverse impacts of climate change. Interventions that support them in building their resilience are not only necessary but urgent.

Building the resilience of smallholder farming and fishing communities requires interventions that provide them greater access to a portfolio of technologies, information, support services, market linkage, and financing. These would enable them to adjust, modify, or change their current production systems and practices in an environmentally friendly way. This process is community-based adaptation.

Climate smart villages (CSV) are platforms that nurture adaptation efforts and build local adaptation capacities. CSVs are geographic locations where action

Adaptation is often considered a high priority and a primary consideration for policy makers and planners because of the current and projected impacts of climate change on agriculture and natural resources. Communities that lack the capacity to respond to climate variability are at great risk. The impacts of climate change on agriculture include the loss of agro-biodiversity, soil degradation, reduction in crop, fish, and livestock productivity, water shortages, reduction of nutritional quality of foods, and possible increases in destructive pests and diseases. With a large population reliant on farming, it is important to find ways of building resilience to climate change.

FOSTERING LOCAL ADAPTATION PLATFORMS: RELATING CLIMATE SMART VILLAGES TO LOCAL AND NATIONAL ADAPTATION PLANS

Authors: Vidallo, Rene; Bayot, Ruvicyn S.; Rosimo, Magnolia; Monville-Oro, Emilita; Gonsalves, Julian; Ilaga, Alicia; Sebastian, Leocadio S.; Manalo, U-Nichols; Baltazar, Perla

Date: 2020-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/106785>

PATHWAYS TO ATTAINING A FOOD SECURE PHILIPPINES THROUGH A COMPETITIVE AND CLIMATE-RESILIENT AGRICULTURE AND FISHERIES SECTOR

Rene Vidallo, Ruvicyn Bayot, Magnolia Rosimo, Emilita Monville-Oro, Julian Gonsalves, Alicia Sebastian, Leocadio Ilaga, Perla Baltazar, U-Nichols

November 2019

Key Messages:

- Climate change is affecting the Philippines' food, agriculture, and fisheries sectors. To help alleviate their situation, the Department of Agriculture (DA) developed the Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation Initiative in Agriculture (AMIA) Program in 2014. Headed by the System-Wide Climate Change Office (SWCCO), the program identified, tested, and promoted climate resilient agriculture (CRA) technologies and approaches, with the climate goal of mainstreaming climate resilience within DA.
- Almost six years into the program, SWCCO and DA Regional Field Offices (RAFOs) have drawn initial sets of lessons and insights from the AMIA villages established across the Philippines in November 2016, as DA observes the Climate Change Consequences Week (CCWCO) and the DA-RAFOs are poised to bring understanding within the DA system the value of engaging for resilience, the relevance of CRA, and the need for mainstreaming, scaling, and sustainability at local levels.
- This document highlights the key messages drawn from climate adaptation efforts and events done with DA-RAFOs across the country. This brief, developed for the Climate Change Consequences Week, offers DA a synthesis of lessons from the AMIA village experience as a bankable model for establishing context-specific, local adaptation platforms for developing and disseminating CRA technologies and processes. This brief also offers valuable insights for the Philippine National Adaptation Plan.

1 Support local platforms for Climate Resilient Agriculture as foundations for resilient agriculture and fisheries

- Climate Resilient Agriculture (CRA) is the Department of Agriculture's approach to building climate resilient food and communities.
- CRA increases agriculture productivity and income in a sustainable and environmentally sound manner; b) builds the capacity of households and food systems to adapt to climate change; and c) reduces greenhouse gas emissions and restores carbon sequestration.
- DA implemented the Adaptation and Mitigation Initiative in Agriculture (AMIA) Program in 2014 to respond to the local challenges of climate change in the agriculture and fisheries communities. It was implemented in three:
 - AMIA 1 (2014) strengthened the capacity of DA to mainstream climate change adaptation at the strategic and operational levels; the National Color-Coded Agriculture Guide (NACAG) (crop management and livestock) in 2017 to inform the local government unit (LGU) management practices that are suitable and appropriate at a given location. This may prove mutually suitable with the 2019 color-coded and it also features eight climate hazards. DA access the map, go to <http://www.farmguidesmag.gov.ph/>
 - AMIA 2 (2016) implemented and evaluated CRA technologies and practices in targeted areas.

PATHWAYS TO ATTAINING A FOOD SECURE PHILIPPINES THROUGH A COMPETITIVE AND CLIMATE-RESILIENT AGRICULTURE AND FISHERIES SECTOR

Authors: Vidallo, Rene; Bayot, Ruvicyn S.; Rosimo, Magnolia; Monville-Oro, Emilita; Gonsalves, Julian; Ilaga, Alicia; Sebastian, Leocadio S.; Manalo, U-Nichols; Baltazar, Perla

Date: 2019-11-30

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/106789>

The AMIA Experience: Supporting local actions for Climate Resilient Agriculture

Rene Vidallo, Ruvicyn Bayot, Magnolia Rosimo, Emilita Monville-Oro, Julian Gonsalves, Alicia Ilaga, Leocadio Sebastian, U-Nichols, Perla Baltazar

November 2019

Key Messages:

- Addressing engagement of local action
- Understanding vulnerability at different scale levels
- Understanding different aspects of and the importance of diversification
- Implementing local CRA technologies and practices with the farmers
- Capitalizing farmers to implement CRA technologies and practices
- Identifying system of extension to facilitate community adaptation and create an enabling environment
- Scaling and operationalizing CRA technologies and approaches
- Developing capacities for sustainability
- Establishing and maintaining partnerships
- Mainstreaming gender
- Identifying champions

The Philippines ranks 5th in the long term global climate risk index 1) to highly vulnerable to increasing frequency of extreme weather events and temperature, extreme rainfall, and sea level rise. Heat change and water stress are the most common climate-related risk factors that affect the country's agriculture and fisheries production. These are reflected in the results of the climate risk vulnerability assessments (CRVA) in almost all AMIA villages facilitated by the International Center for Tropical Agriculture (CIAT), partner state colleges and universities, and the Department of Agriculture - Regional Field Offices (RAFOs).

The emerging effects of climate change are worst among the poor and vulnerable production farmers and fisherfolk. Hence, climate resilient agriculture (CRA) integrates local adaptation, mitigation and mitigation agents in the implementation of sustainable agricultural practice. DA's System-Wide Climate Change Office (SWCCO) implemented the Adaptation and Mitigation Initiative in Agriculture (AMIA) Program to respond to the challenges of climate change in the agriculture and fisheries communities. The initiative enables and empowers local communities to manage climate risks while pursuing sustainable livelihoods. This is being

1

THE AMIA EXPERIENCE: SUPPORTING LOCAL ACTIONS FOR CLIMATE RESILIENT AGRICULTURE

Authors: Vidallo, Rene; Bayot, Ruvicyn S.; Rosimo, Magnolia; Monville-Oro, Emilita; Gonsalves, Julian; Ilaga, Alicia; Sebastian, Leocadio S.; Manalo, U-Nichols; Baltazar, Perla

Date: 2019-11-30

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/106787>

Info Note

Scaling the capacities to adapt to a changing climate

Experiences of the AMIA Climate Resilient Villages, Philippines

Jana Koerner, Ruvicyn S. Bayot, Magpie Rosimo, Rene Vidallo, Julian Gonsalves

November 2019

Key messages:

- AMIA villages have the necessary ingredients to develop the system-wide innovation platforms.
- AMIA Village leaders act as the nexus between farmer communities, the local government and the local enabling environment.
- With technical knowledge on CRA widely being available, only financial support remains the key missing elements in establishing and sustaining an enabling environment.
- Local knowledge in combination with technical knowledge serves as a strong driver of innovation, capacity and learning formats, and M&E.
- Main challenges related to technical assistance of the AMIA village leaders focus on resources and the enabling environment.
- High-potential needs assessments of the innovation capacities could help the AMIA village project to take their capacity building activities from a farmer-centric to a system-wide perspective.

The fast advancing climate change calls for accelerated scaling of agricultural innovations. The climate-resilient agriculture (CRA) concept in the Philippines requires agri-industrial development with climate responsiveness. Similar to climate-resilient agriculture, CRA in fisheries and aquaculture also requires a systems approach.

Conolidating technical and financial capacities

The need for constant adaptation in a changing climate points to an increased importance of the train-the-trainer adaptation capacities across all levels. This also means that

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SCALING THE CAPACITIES TO ADAPT TO A CHANGING CLIMATE: EXPERIENCES OF THE AMIA CLIMATE RESILIENT VILLAGES, PHILIPPINES

Authors: Koerner J, Bayot RS, Rosimo M, Vidallo R, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2019-11

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/105717>

Mapping the Research and Development Agenda of Food Systems in the Philippines
 February 21, 2019 | Book 1.1 | James Lee Crute | Working Paper

WORKSHOP INFORMATION NOTE

Initiating a new food system research and innovation platform in the Philippines

Key messages

- 1. There are research gaps in the state of food and nutrition situation in the Philippines but the food system research agenda still needs to be reorg and reinv the research agenda.
- 2. The household plays an essential role in ensuring food security.
- 3. Access to food and food is affected by the economic status of the household.
- 4. Good governance is necessary for the implementation of food systems research and development programs.
- 5. Implementation of the Food Security, Food, Bioeconomics, and Consumer Segments requires the food system.
- 6. There is a pressing need to create a comprehensive food base for the Philippines food system.
- 7. Promotion of food health and nutrition security should be at the level of all the levels of government and other sectors of society.

MAPPING THE RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT AGENDA OF FOOD SYSTEMS IN THE PHILIPPINES

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction and International Center for Tropical Agriculture

Date: 2019-09-26

Link: <http://bit.ly/2YaPzOD>

Info Note

Addressing gender-based impacts of climate change

A case study of Guinayangan, Philippines
 Magnolia Rosimo, Julian Gonsalves, Johannes Gammelgaard, Rene Vidallo, Emilita Oro

Key messages

- 1. Climate change manifests through the impact of particularly extreme weather events such as the development of typhoons and droughts.
- 2. Gender-based impacts from the effects of climate change are felt more. This includes being more vulnerable to natural disasters, less access to resources, and less control over decisions.
- 3. Gender-based impacts from the effects of climate change are felt more. This includes being more vulnerable to natural disasters, less access to resources, and less control over decisions.
- 4. Gender-based impacts from the effects of climate change are felt more. This includes being more vulnerable to natural disasters, less access to resources, and less control over decisions.

ADDRESSING GENDER-BASED IMPACTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE: A CASE STUDY OF GUINAYANGAN, PHILIPPINES

Authors: Rosimo, Magnolia; Gonsalves, Julian; Gammelgaard, Johanna; Vidallo, Rene; Monville-Oro, Emilita

Date: 2018-12-06

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/98473>

Info Note

Equity, empowerment and gender relations

A literature review of special relevance for climate-smart agriculture programming
 Francis Villavicencio, Magnolia Rosimo, Rene Vidallo, Emilita Oro, Julian Gonsalves

Key messages

- 1. Women are more vulnerable to the effects of climate change than men.
- 2. The lack of gender-responsive approaches can hinder the implementation of climate-smart agriculture programming.
- 3. Improved access to resources, information, and services can enhance the resilience of women and men.

EQUITY, EMPOWERMENT AND GENDER RELATIONS: A LITERATURE REVIEW OF SPECIAL RELEVANCE FOR CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE PROGRAMMING

Authors: Villavicencio, Francia; Rosimo, Magnolia; Vidallo, Rene; Monville-Oro, Emilita; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2018-12-06

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/99061>

A GENDER-RESPONSIVE APPROACH TO COMMUNITY-BASED ADAPTATION IN GUINAYANGAN, QUEZON

Authors: Bayot RS, Palima CM, Punzalan BR, Vidallo RR, Gonsalves JF.

Date: 2021-11

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/115855>

SCALING OF CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE VIA CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGES IN SOUTHEAST ASIA: INSIGHTS AND LESSONS FROM VIETNAM, LAOS, PHILIPPINES, CAMBODIA AND MYANMAR

Authors: Barbon WJ, Punzalan B, Wassman R, Bui VL, Vidallo R, Villanueva J, Talsma T, Bayot R, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-11

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/115833>

COCONUT-BASED SYSTEMS IN THE PHILIPPINES: INTENSIFICATION AND DIVERSIFICATION WITH CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE

Authors: Manilay A, Cabriole MA, Itliong K, Jordan R, Rosimo M, Monville-Oro E, Barbon WJ, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-10

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/115290>

COVID-19 IMPACT ON LOCAL AGRI-FOOD SYSTEM IN CAMBODIA, MYANMAR, AND THE PHILIPPINES: FINDINGS FROM A RAPID ASSESSMENT

Authors: Espino A, Itliong K, Ruba CD, Thy O, Barbon WJ, Monville-Oro E, Gummati S, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-06

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/113843>

LOCAL FOOD SYSTEMS IN CAMBODIA, MYANMAR, AND THE PHILIPPINES: PERSPECTIVE FROM THE LOCAL COMMUNITIES

Authors: Espino, Apple; Monville-Oro, Emily; Barbon, Wilson John; Ruba, Christine Dianne; Gummadi, Sridhar; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2021-05-28

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/113826>

TRANSFORMING FOOD SYSTEMS UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE: LOCAL TO GLOBAL POLICY AS A CATALYST FOR CHANGE

Authors: Rawe T, Antonelli M, Chatrchyan A, Clayton T, Fanzo J, Gonsalves J, Matthews A, Nierenberg D, Zurek M.

Date: 2019-06

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/101601>

A NEW RELEVANCE AND BETTER PROSPECTS FOR WIDER UPTAKE OF SOCIAL LEARNING WITHIN CGIAR

Author: Gonsalves J.

Date: 2013-09

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/33719>

TRANSFORMING LOCAL LIVELIHOODS TO COMMUNITY ENTERPRISES IN GUINAYANGAN, QUEZON PROVINCE

Authors: Tacugue MCJ, Tolentino FS, Vidallo RR, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-11

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/115923>

PORTFOLIO OF CLIMATE RESILIENT OPTIONS FOR FARMING AND FISHING COMMUNITIES IN GUINAYANGAN, QUEZON

Authors: Rosimo MM, Vidallo RR, Dalusag JB, Bernardo EB, Monville-Oro E, Rosales BO, Cabriole ME, Gonsalves JF.

Date: 2021-11

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/115790>

PORTFOLIO OF CLIMATE RESILIENT OPTIONS FOR FARMING AND FISHING COMMUNITIES IN GUINAYANGAN, QUEZON

Authors: Mendez KS, Vidallo RR, Rosimo MM, Angeles DR, Rosales BO, Bernardo EB, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-08

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/114770>

PORTFOLIO OF CLIMATE RESILIENT OPTIONS FOR FARMING AND FISHING COMMUNITIES IN IVISAN, CAPIZ

Authors: Mendez KS, Vidallo RR, Rosimo MM, Servano GS Jr, Urdelas FG, Bernales LL, Bernardo EB, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-08

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/114772>

LEARNING GROUPS: REFINING TECHNOLOGIES AND SOCIAL PROCESSES FOR CLIMATE RESILIENT AGRICULTURE

Authors: Mendez KS, Vidallo RR, Rosimo M, Angeles DR, Bernardo EB, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-08

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/114778>

COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF NATIVE PIGS AS A CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE OPTION IN THE PHILIPPINES

Authors: Manilay A, Monville-Oro E, Barbon WJ, Ruba CD, Vidallo R, Rosimo M, Cabriole MA, Gummadi S, Gonsalves J, Rondon M.

Date: 2021-07

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/114389>

EVALUATING THE VIABILITY OF FAMILY FARMING IN MARAGONDON, CAVITE

Authors: Valerio, A.T., Onuh, W.O., and Dalusag, J.B.

Date: 2021

Link: <http://bit.ly/3ulc24T>

ADAPTATION STRATEGIES FOR MANAGING CLIMATE AND ENVIRONMENTAL RISKS WHILE PURSUING SUSTAINABLE AND COMPETITIVE LIVELIHOODS: EXPERIENCES FROM AMIA VILLAGES

Authors: Department of Agriculture; International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2020-12-21

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/111532>

PARTICIPATORY CLIMATE RISK MAPPING: BUILDING LOCAL ADAPTATION CAPACITIES. A CASE FROM IVISAN, CAPIZ, PHILIPPINES

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2020-12-07

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/110422>

ESTABLISHING CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGES IN THE ASEAN REGION TO IMPROVE FOOD SECURITY AND RESILIENCY IN LOCAL COMMUNITIES

Author: SEARCA

Date: 2019-12-23

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/106893>

APPRECIATION WORKSHOP ON CLIMATE-RESILIENT AGRICULTURE FOR THE LOCAL GOVERNMENT OFFICIALS OF QUEZON PROVINCE (4TH DISTRICT): A WORKSHOP REPORT

Authors: Bayot, Ruvicyn S.; Vidallo, Rene; Palima, Carlo; Laco, Jonalyn; Jordan, Ruel; Locaba, Rico; Rosales, Belina; Luistro, Aida; Anda, Girsky; Obligado, Maria Ella Cecilia

Date: 2019-11-30

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/107320>

CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE APPRECIATION EVENT FOR THE MEMBERS OF THE PHILIPPINE NETWORK OF ENVIRONMENTAL JOURNALISTS

Authors: Vidallo, Rene; Bayot, Ruvicyn S.; Anunciado, Ma. Sheila

Date: 2019-04-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/107784>

LEVERAGING NUTRITION OUTCOMES IN SCHOOLS: A SYNTHESIS OF SCHOOL FEEDING, SCHOOL GARDENING AND NUTRITION EDUCATION EXPERIENCES

Authors: International Institute of Rural
Reconstruction, International
Development Research Centre

Date: 2018

Link: <http://hdl.handle.net/10625/57228>

INTEGRATED COMMUNITY FOOD PRODUCTION: A COMPENDIUM OF CLIMATE-RESILIENT AGRICULTURE OPTIONS

Author: Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2016-07-05

Link: <http://hdl.handle.net/10568/75968>

CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE PRIMER (VIETNAMESE LANGUAGE)

Authors: Simelton E, Van Hai L, Dinh Hoa L, Vidallo
R, Gonsalves J

Date: 2016-06

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/89902>

External link to download:

<http://www.worldagroforestry.org/region/sea/publications/detail?pubID=3577>

PATHWAYS TO ATTAINING A FOOD SECURE PHILIPPINES THROUGH A COMPETITIVE AND CLIMATE-RESILIENT AGRI-FISHERIES SECTOR (POSTERS)

Authors: Vidallo, Rene; Bayot, Ruvicyn S.; Monville-Oro, Emilita; Gonsalves, Julian; Ilaga, Alicia; Sebastian, Leocadio S.; Manalo, U-Nichols; Baltazar, Perla

Date: 2020-05

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/108278>

FARMER LEARNING GROUPS

Authors: Vidallo, Rene; Bayot, Ruvicyn S.; Rosimo, Magnolia; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2019-12

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/107333>

PARTICIPATORY ACTION RESEARCH

Authors: Vidallo, Rene; Bayot, Ruvicyn S.; Rosimo, Magnolia; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2019-12

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/107334>

COMMUNITY SUPPORT FACILITIES

Authors: Vidallo, Rene; Bayot, Ruvicyn S.; Rosimo, Magnolia; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2019-12

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/107332>

IMPACT AREAS

Authors: Vidallo, Rene; Bayot, Ruvicyn S.; Rosimo, Magnolia; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2019-12

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/107335>

COMMUNITY INNOVATION FUND

Authors: Vidallo, Rene; Bayot, Ruvicyn S.; Rosimo, Magnolia; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2019-12

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/107331>

CLIMATE RESILIENT AGRICULTURE: EDUCATIONAL/TRAINING POSTERS SERIES

Author: Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2016-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/71099>

SCHOOL GARDENS: FOR BETTER HEALTH, NUTRITION AND EDUCATIONAL OUTCOMES

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2016-10-14

Link: <https://bit.ly/3GJTioZ>

LET'S START GARDENING FOR HEALTHIER FAMILIES!

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2016-10-14

Link: <https://bit.ly/3CJWhxH>

PREPARE YOUR CHILDREN'S FUTURE, START WITH GOOD NUTRITION!

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction
 Date: 2013-05-06
 Link: <https://bit.ly/3k2PqIj>

GET TO KNOW THE NUTRITIOUS INDIGENOUS VEGETABLES

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction
 Date: 2017-02-20
 Link: <https://bit.ly/3wfnqGT>

NATIVE PIGS: A CLIMATE RESILIENT BUSINESS ENTERPRISE

Authors: Rosales, Belina; Palima, Carlo; Hernandez, Gerry; Gonsalves, Julian; Rosimo, Maggie; Santiago, Rene; Vidallo, Rene; Locaba, Rico; Soksophors, Yim

Date: 2020-04-28

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/108081>

TAPNO MAAWATAN TI PANAGBALIW TI KLIMA (CLIMATE CHANGE): LIBRITO PARA KADAGITI OPISIAL TI GOBIERNO-LOCAL DITTOY PILIPINAS

Authors: Gonsalves J, Vidallo R, Oro E, Dalusag J, Barbon WJ, Rosimo M, Jordan J, Romero J, Servano G, Baguilat I, Rosales B, Narte J, Puno A, Narte R, Bernales ELL, Navarra EV, Briones C, Sebastian L.

Date: 2018-09

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/99578>

CLIMATE RESILIENCE IN AGRICULTURE: KEY CONCEPTS FOR COMMUNITY-BASED ADAPTATION

Authors: Gonsalves, Julian; Vidallo, Rene; Monville-Oro, Emilita; Dalusag, Joanna; Barbon, Wilson J.; Jordan, Jonna; Rosimo, Maggie; Servano, Gonzalo; Lorenzo, Maria Cristina; Mendez, Kharla Vianca; Rosales, Belina; Narte, Julieta; Puno, Arnel; Narte, Russel; Bernales, Lorna L.; Navarra, Eduardo V; Sebastian, Leocadio S.; Joven, Bernadette; Baconguis, Rowena; Tolentino, Caress

Date: 2016-11-25

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/79434>

CLIMATE SMART VILLAGES: KEY CONCEPTS (A PRIMER FOR CCAFS PARTNERS IN SOUTHEAST ASIA)

Authors: Gonsalves, Julian; Sebastian, Leocadio S.; Joven, B.; Amutan C; Lucerna A

Date: 2015-11-25

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/69005>

CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURE: A PRIMER FOR LOCAL GOVERNMENT OFFICIALS IN THE PHILIPPINES

Authors: Vidallo, R.; Gonsalves, Julian; Monville-Oro, Emilita; Dalusag, Joanna; Barbon, Wilson J.; Jordan J; Rosimo M; Romero, J.; Servano G; Baguilat I; Rosales, B.; Narte J; Purdon, Mark; Narte R; Bernales, Lorna L.; Navarra EV; Sebastian, Leocadio S.

Date: 2015-10-30

Link: <http://hdl.handle.net/10568/68835>

UNDERSTANDING CLIMATE CHANGE: A PRIMER FOR LOCAL GOVERNMENT OFFICIALS IN THE PHILIPPINES

Authors: Vidallo R, Gonsalves J, Oro E, Dalusag J, Barbon WJ, Jordan J, Rosimo M, Romero J, Servano G, Baguilat I, Rosales B, Narte J, Puno A, Narte R, Bernales ELL, Navarra EV, Sebastian L.

Date: 2015-10

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/68834>

FACILITATING COMMUNITY-BASED ADAPTATION THROUGH CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE - TRAINER'S RESOURCE BOOK

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2021-10

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/115915>

EIGHT GUIDE STEPS FOR SETTING UP A CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGE: A TRAINER'S GUIDE

Authors: Gonsalves, Julian; Baguilat, Irish; Bantayan, Rosario; Bernardo, Eisen Bernard; Sebastian, Leocadio S.

Date: 2020-03-12

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/107725>

FIELD GUIDE IN CONDUCTING PVA

Author: Rosimo, Magnolia

Type: Manual

Date: 2020-03-26

Link: <http://bit.ly/39Zz3GJ>

8 GUIDE STEPS FOR SETTING UP A CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGE (CSV)

Authors: Sebastian, Leocadio S.; Gonsalves, Julian; Bernardo, Eisen Bernard

Date: 2019-09-05

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/103527>

9 STEPS TO SCALE CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE: LESSONS AND EXPERIENCES FROM THE CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGES IN MY LOI, VIETNAM AND GUINAYANGAN, PHILIPPINES

Authors: Le Thi Tam; Vidallo, Rene; Simelton, Elisabeth; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2018-12-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/101921>

BRINGING GARDENS FROM ONE SCHOOL TO ANOTHER

One of the flagship programs of the Department of Education (DepEd) that is highly promoted by the Division Office of Cavite Province is the maintenance of school gardens. The gardening to school is challenging because of inadequate water, lack of space, lack of garden tools, presence of pest and other diseases, poor soil, limited time of teachers in gardening, insufficient knowledge in food production, poor drainage, presence of stray animals, stealing of plants, and natural calamities such as floods.

On 2013, DepEd - Cavite Province, in partnership with the International Institute of Rural Reconstruction (IIRR), advocated the improvement of nutritional status of school-aged children in Cavite through the enhancement of the *Gulayan sa Paaralan* Program (School Garden) and the School Based Feeding Program through the Sustainable Agriculture Techno-Instructional Education Expansion for Community and School Health (SATE-ECCH). This program intends to reinforce agriculture teachers' knowledge and skills in setting up and maintaining school gardens, as well as strengthen the link of the garden to the feeding program. Trainings were conducted to discuss *Sila* intensive gardening (SIG), key essential elements of soil management, crop management, seed and seedling management, and pest management. Enhancement of *Gulayan sa Paaralan* and School Based Feeding Program was improved through the support of IIRR.

The DepEd - Cavite Province implemented this program not only to reinforce the value of growing vegetables among the students but also to promote among the people the importance of eating nutritious indigenous vegetables. The program is relevant because it introduces children that gardening is an exciting and profitable venture.

APPROACHES USED

To successfully implement the School Garden Program, here are some of the approaches employed by the DepEd - Cavite Province Division:

Garden Site Improvement in Schools. School heads and agriculture teachers selected garden sites with Education Program Supervisors providing technical assistance.

Capacity Training for Agriculture Teachers. To update the knowledge and skills of agriculture teachers on new agriculture technologies for school gardens, capacity training were conducted including personal and resource trainals. Resource persons came from the Department of Agriculture (DA) - Region IV-A, membership office of Rural Reconstruction (IIRR), Agriculture Training Institute - (ATI) and Office of Provincial Agriculture (OPA).

Information Education and Environmental Advocacy. Lessons on climate change and global warming were integrated in the EPP and TLE subjects. Teachers attended a training on disaster preparedness and conducted information and awareness campaign. Agriculture teachers initiated environmental activities in school such as composting.

Appreciation Seminars for School Heads and District Supervisors. To re-visit the interest of school officials

CAVITE PROVINCE: BRINGING GARDENS FROM ONE SCHOOL TO ANOTHER

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-05-31

Link: <https://bit.ly/3mAOzAl>

Citywide Improvement of Garden Schools: A Schools Division Initiative

The City of Dasmariñas is the largest city in Cavite Province. With its increasing population, comes an increase in the number of severely malnourished and wasted students in public elementary schools. In school year 2017-2018, there were around 5,923 severely malnourished and 4,264 wasted Kindergarten to 6th Grade students in the City. The Schools Division Office aims to improve the nutritional status of severely malnourished and wasted pupils and increase classroom performance using the Integrated School Nutrition Model, which was introduced by the International Institute of Rural Reconstruction (IIRR) and the Food and Nutrition Research Institute (FNRI). This model connects the *Gulayan sa Paaralan* Program (School Garden), Supplementary School Feeding Program (SSFP), and nutrition education.

The Schools Division is encouraging public schools in the City to adopt the model but many schools were encountering challenges with their gardens. Some coordinators were worried about the poor soil quality of their gardens and of the frequent incidences of typhoons, heavy rains, and droughts. Others were concerned about the pests and diseases that attack the crops. And there were also some who complain about backlogging planting spaces in their schools or the lack of support from parents in sustaining the garden.

The Schools Division of Dasmariñas are addressing these challenges through the following activities:

Seed Exchange: A seed exchange was conducted last February 2017 at Francisco E. Bangoy Memorial School. It was participated by 28 elementary schools and was supported by a seed exchange district policy issued by the City Division.

Lighthouse and Crop Museum: There are 5 lighthouse schools established in 5 districts of the division: Dasmariñas 1 Central School, Letaon Elementary School, Malara Elementary, Palajaran Elementary School, and San Isidro Elementary School. These schools lead in promoting the *Gulayan sa Paaralan* Program within the division and in collaborating with other stakeholders.

The Division of Dasmariñas issued Division Memorandum no. 55, a 2017 titled Establishment of Crop Museum, which serve as a source of viable seeds for other schools and communities. Three crop museums were set up in the Division: San Cruz Elementary School, San Nicolas Elementary School and Pata Elementary School.

Division School Garden: The Division School garden leads in showcasing good practices in the school garden. Hence, it established a garden with the support of external stakeholders and was maintained by the parents, teachers, learners and local government units. Support from the Department of Agriculture, in partnership with the Department of Agriculture, the School Division trained teachers on organic vegetable production and 28 teachers were awarded with a National Certificate II in Vegetable Production. The Department of Agriculture also conducted a *Gulayan sa Paaralan* Training on October 13, 2017 at Division Office of Cavite Province.

DASMARIÑAS CITY: CITYWIDE IMPROVEMENT OF GARDEN SCHOOLS: A SCHOOLS DIVISION INITIATIVE

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-06-05

Link: <https://bit.ly/3q62qki>

GarNESupp in an Urban Setting

Everything starts from scratch but through vision, faith, hard work and collaboration, nothing is impossible to achieve. The magic need is synergy and luck is the tale of GarNESupp (Gardening, Nutrition Education, and Supplementary Feeding) in the Schools Division of Imus City. It started in 2013 when it established a partnership with the International Institute of Rural Reconstruction (IIRR), which aimed to teach gardening to 6 to 12 learners to resolve malnutrition among schoolchildren.

Thuburan Elementary School was chosen as a sentinel school and generated outcomes and evidence that was used in the advocacy for an integrated nutrition model. The model aimed students and learner in significant results. It improved the nutritional status of learners from severely malnourished and wasted to becoming normal and a diverse and nutritious-relevant school garden was sustained. Community participation was also established as children, parents, and teachers started to embrace and recognize the value of vegetables in their respective diets. Even the private sector and the LGU were engaged.

The remarkable improvement made Thuburan Elementary School a focal point for research on the integrated approach. Detailed garden production data, nutritional impact studies and nutritional education outcomes were among those carefully monitored.

Issues encountered

Imus City is a progressive city in the region but due to the limited space, the standard and minimum requirements for Garden and Feeding was not met. The trainings designed to be attended by all school heads and Education Program Supervisors were not realized due to overlapping schedules. Timely submission and collating of reports of coordination hinder the submission of reports since IRR, SSFP, GFP, and NARIE are only ancillary works or tasks of teachers. External stakeholders also have low commitment to the program.

Multiplying Success

The tale of synergy of the Schools Division of Imus City was supported through the establishment of systems in the three components of GarNESupp model. The Schools Division of Imus City conducted a series of training workshops about the concept of file-intensive Gardening, Nutrition Education, Supplementary Feeding Program, Research, Entrepreneurship, and Partnership.

A Facebook Chat Group was created as a platform to exchange ideas between schools and for easy access on the submission of reports. Uniform Resource

IMUS CITY: GarNESupp IN AN URBAN SETTING

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-05-31

Link: <https://bit.ly/3GMXzu7>

ENGAGING REGIONAL OFFICIALS IN THE GARNESUPP PROJECT: Region 4A

Region IV-A consists of five (5) provinces: Cavite, Laguna, Batangas, Marikina, and Quezon. Based on the 2013 Census of Population (CEN) of the Philippine Statistics Authority, the region is the most populous region in the Philippines and has a population of 14,647,916 people. It is also the 12th largest region in the country in terms of land area, which is 16,873.31 sqm.

Department of Education (DepEd) Region IV-A's primary goal is to improve the schools' performance by enhancing the capabilities of teachers and school managers. It led in delivering services to all schools, both public and private elementary and secondary schools, to achieve quality education and produce individuals who are academically prepared, value-laden, and physically fit.

DepEd Central Office, Region IV-A has the highest percentage of malnourished and severely malnourished learners among the 17 regions in the Philippines, for School Year 2017-2018. The malnourished and severely malnourished learners were 146,202 and 8,159 learners, respectively.

The number of feeding beneficiaries in Region IV-A for School Year 2017-2018 is 347,641, which is slightly lower compared to last year, where there were 367,399 beneficiaries. The trend in number of beneficiaries in the region each school year goes up and down.

DepEd Nutrition Program

To address the problem of malnutrition, the Department of Education, through its Regional and Division Offices, established several nutrition programs and policies: the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) or the Galawan sa Paaralang Program (GPP) or the School Garden Program.

The SBFP is one of DepEd's programs that tackle nutrition. It aims to rehabilitate at least 70% of severely malnourished beneficiaries to normal nutritional status at the end of 120 feeding days, ensure 80% to 90% classroom attendance of the beneficiaries, and improve the children's health and nutrition values and behavior.

The region has 20 schools division offices, 252 school districts, 2740 public elementary schools, and 214 public secondary schools with a total enrollment of 3,792,233 pupils for SY 2017-2018 in both public and private elementary and secondary schools.

Nutritional status of learners in Region IV-A

Absent from lack of classrooms and teachers, one of the problems of DepEd Region IV-A is the high prevalence of malnutrition among its learners. Based on the consolidated data of the Nutritional Status from the

ENGAGING REGIONAL OFFICIALS IN THE GARNESUPP PROJECT: REGION 4A

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-05-31

Link: <https://bit.ly/2ZXtw2l>

MOBILIZING FUNDS FOR INTEGRATED SCHOOL NUTRITION PROGRAM

Julugan Elementary School is one of the biggest public schools in the Municipality of Tanza in Cavite Province. Established in 1910, it is a great school with 50 teachers and 2,204 pupils from Kindergarten to Grade Six - 209 of which are School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) recipients. It has a total land area of 10,078 square meters, with 200 square meters allocated for the school garden. Most of the school children live near the neighborhood where more facilities exist from families.

With different fundraising initiatives to build a feeding center for SBFP recipients, sustain the school garden, and establish a nutrition education work relationship with the local government units (LGU) and stakeholders.

During the School of the School Address (SOSEA), the school sought the support of the parents, LGUs, and other stakeholders in the implementation of the Integrated School Nutrition Program. Unfolding the program's benefits to their children, the parents responded positively and agreed to participate in the fundraising activities. The school created planning and working committees composed of nutrition education coordinators, teachers, Parents and Teacher Association (PTA) officers, and representatives from the LGU. They led the planning and implementation of fundraising activities.

The school leveraged the Rev. My. Plinio M. Salas M. of Padre Pio Square and fundraising campaign. For three months, funds and signatures were called every last Friday of the month. Students who have collected the highest amount of money and gathered the most number of signatures from friends, neighbors, and other supporters led by crowned Mr. and Mrs. Julugan Elementary School. The funds generated from this activity were used for the construction of the Feeding Center and purchase of furniture and fixtures for same.

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Fundraising initiatives

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When the Integrated School Nutrition Program - a program that integrates Galawan sa Paaralang or school garden, Supplementary Feeding and Nutrition Education was introduced, the school was willing to do what possible means to make the implementation successful. However, the school had inadequate resources to fund the program and invest in facilities. To address this limitation, the school principal and teachers came

SENTINEL SCHOOL: JULUGAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL MOBILIZING FUNDS FOR INTEGRATED SCHOOL NUTRITION PROGRAM

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-05-07

Link: <https://bit.ly/3nMoyNK>

NUTRITION EDUCATION AT TINABUNAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

Why should we educate our students about nutrition? Because the benefits are too valuable. From students making healthier choices to improvement in their academic performance, nutrition education can benefit families and communities.

In school year 2014-2017, Tinabunan Elementary School implemented the School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) to address the undernutrition and food insecurity of 147 students - and the Galawan sa Paaralang School Gardening Program - to supply vegetables and cooking ingredients to the SBFP. These programs were implemented using the Integrated School Nutrition Model, where nutrition education played a critical role in engaging not just the students but the teachers, parents, and the entire community as well.

The Health/Child teacher educates parents and guardians how to include indigenous vegetables in daily meals while educator parents conduct cooking demonstrations. The school also organizes cooking contests to showcase the talent and skills of parents in using indigenous vegetables. The winning menu is served in the feeding program and school canteen. Nutrition education coordinators provide feedback to parents (usually during parent-teacher conferences), village officials, teachers, and other community members. Filters on different nutrition-related topics are distributed to parents every month to educate and encourage them to apply their knowledge at home. Teachers also visit the homes of SBFP recipients who skip the feeding program to inform their parents or guardians about healthy and affordable meals. A copy of the recipe book that uses indigenous vegetables is

nutrition information of crops is displayed on small signposts. The garden teacher also teaches gardening and planting. A Nutrition Education Learning Resource Center (N-ELRC) was also established in the school where students can read books and materials related to nutrition. Teachers can also bring their students here at any of their lessons. A health board was installed near the main gate to exhibit nutrition-related information like recipes and pictures of vegetables and these are changed every quarter.

The Health/Child teacher educates parents and guardians how to include indigenous vegetables in daily meals while educator parents conduct cooking demonstrations. The school also organizes cooking contests to showcase the talent and skills of parents in using indigenous vegetables. The winning menu is served in the feeding program and school canteen. Nutrition education coordinators provide feedback to parents (usually during parent-teacher conferences), village officials, teachers, and other community members. Filters on different nutrition-related topics are distributed to parents every month to educate and encourage them to apply their knowledge at home. Teachers also visit the homes of SBFP recipients who skip the feeding program to inform their parents or guardians about healthy and affordable meals. A copy of the recipe book that uses indigenous vegetables is

New to school

Tinabunan Elementary School integrated nutrition topics in class subjects and taught them during flag ceremonies. Teachers and students share nutrition-related information through songs and skits recitals, emphasizing the benefits of eating indigenous vegetables planted in the school garden. Educational videos about the importance of eating nutritious food are also shown to SBFP beneficiaries at the feeding center. The school garden is used as a learning venue for students, where

SENTINEL SCHOOL: NUTRITION EDUCATION AT TINABUNAN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-05-31

Link: <https://bit.ly/3nRYnWe>

Make Nutrition Education FUN!

Nutrition Education is one of the key complements to health and nutrition programs in schools. It helps children understand the value of eating safe, adequate and healthy food for growth and development.

To make nutrition learning fun and exciting in more schools, the Integrated School Nutrition Project has compiled creative nutrition education activities from across Region 4A.

Vegetable Hunt
Students race to identify the garden plants used to cook the canteen menu of the day. Feeding beneficiaries may also play this game and whoever wins gets to the tray line first.

Nutri Quiz
Can be played by children or parents, participants are grouped into 4-5 members. The first group to raise their flag gets the chance to answer the nutrition trivia question. The game master may also show photos of an indigenous vegetable to be identified.

Nutri-Puzzle
A figure of an image depicting healthy habits or an indigenous vegetable with a short key message about good nutrition. The first group to build the puzzle reads the message aloud and wins.

Nutri-Bingo
Instead of numbers, Nutri Bingo Cards contain words or phrases related to good nutrition. The game master reads questions from the list while players mark the box that correspond to the correct answer. The first player to form the agreed pattern shouts "Nutri!" The catch is that the game master will check if the answers along the pattern is indeed correct.

Farm-to-Table Cook Fest
Parent and child tandem compete for the most innovative, nutritious and delicious recipe they could develop out of the vegetables they can harvest from the school garden.

More Nutrition education methods and materials are accessible at <https://iirr.org.ph/nutrition-education/>

DID YOU KNOW?
More than 20% of school children in the Philippines are underweight and too short for their age to achieve the average consumption of fruits & vegetables per person in the 20 countries compared with recommended 1.06-2.12 kg/year.

MAKE NUTRITION EDUCATION FUN!

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2020-04-06

Link: <https://bit.ly/3BFGxun>

IIRR INSTITUTE OF RURAL RECONSTRUCTION

Nutri-bingo!

Gabay para sa 'game master' o facilitators

Ano ang nutri-bingo?
Ang nutri-bingo ay binago sa pinagmulat na "nutritiyon" at "bingo", na'y mayay at nakakaangapang pamanamagang pagpapali sa kababatahan ng wastong nutritiyon. Ang laroing ito ay maaaring baguhin para maging angkop sa mga lokal.

Layunin ng nutri-bingo:
Nagpapali ang nutri-bingo sa mas mapalawak ang kalamayan ng mga mamamagang tungkol sa wastong nutritiyon at mga masustansiyang pagkain tulad ng mga katubong pagpapali ng mga lokal na produktong pagkain.

Mga kaalaman:
1. Nutri-bingo cards, 2. Nutri-bingo answer key (for facilitators), 3. Balpog, 4. Prerapi (optional)

Papaano ito gumamit?

1. Ang nutri-bingo ay binago sa larang "bingo" na pinagmulat ng bingo-cards—kung ano ang unang nakalathala ng wastong pattern ay ipagpapali sa mga magulang.
2. Itay maaaring lamang ng pang-indibidwal o grupo.
3. Maaaring bumagay ng 5-10 grupo: bawat grupo ng pagpapali 1 nutri-bingo card. Kung may 10 grupo, 10 magkakaibang nutri-bingo cards ang pagpapali.
4. Makalathala sa nutri-bingo cards ang mga lokal na katubong pagkain sa wastong nutritiyon. Bubansin ng game master ang mga katubong pagkain ng lokal na katubong pagkain ng mga lokal. Ang bawat matatag na salita ay dapat magbigay kasama sa bawat game master upang hindi makapali sa pagpapali.
5. Maaabuhin ng mga magulang ang tamang sagot sa karaming nutri-bingo cards. Ang unang nakalathala ng wastong pattern ay ipagpapali ng "Nutri-bingo!"
6. Gawing malubog ng game master ang nutri-bingo card kung tama ang wastong pattern.

Papaano maaaring balenting pattern?

Ang maaaring baguhin ng pagpapali ng tamang sagot ay IRR.

NUTRI-BINGO!

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2017-07-06

Link: <https://bit.ly/31sxMaE>

IIRR INSTITUTE OF RURAL RECONSTRUCTION

Nutripuzzle: Paano ito gawin?

Gabay para sa paggawa ng sariling nutripuzzle

Ano ang nutripuzzle?
Ang nutripuzzle ay binago sa pinagmulat na salitang "nutritiyon" at "puzzle", na'y mayay at nakakaangapang pamanamagang pagpapali sa kababatahan ng wastong nutritiyon. Ang laroing ito ay maaaring baguhin para maging angkop sa mga lokal.

Bakit nutripuzzle?
Nagpapali ang nutripuzzle sa mas mapalawak ang kalamayan ng mga mamamagang tungkol sa wastong nutritiyon, karaming, pagpapali ng mga masustansiyang pagkain tulad ng mga katubong pagkain.

Mga kaalaman:

- 1 printed template ng nutripuzzle sa board paper (mas maubli kung mas makapali sa papel)
- 1 long folder o kaya matigas na papel o cardboard
- Painted o glue
- Scotch tape
- Scissors
- 1 brown envelope para maglagay

Papaano gawin ang nutripuzzle?

1. Dahan-dahan silat ang printed template ng nutripuzzle sa folder gamit ang pandikit o glue, lusakang damhan ang pagkain ng glue upang hindi kumalat ang lik ng printed template.
2. Lagyan o dikitan ng scotch tape ang buong dikit na nutripuzzle template—ito ay magpapali ng proteksyon sa bawat ito mas mapalawak ang ito ang katubong ng nutripuzzle.
3. Guguhin ang nutripuzzle template ng sarili sa gabay sa linya para mabuo ang pakaabuhang puzzle pieces, lumina sa pagpapali ang priwang o magh.
4. Ang matatag kababatang bahagi ng folder ay maaaring gawing frame ng puzzle. Gumuhin ng sapit na strip ng folder na ang sulat ay karaming ng haba at taas ng nutripuzzle template. Makit ito ng matatag na pagpapali sa kababatang folder na nakat sa lik ng nutripuzzle. Ang folder strip ay magpapali ng gabay ng frame para sa pagpapali ng nabuong nutripuzzle.
5. Gumamit ng brown envelope para maglagay ng nutripuzzle.

NUTRIPUZZLE

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2017-07-06

Link: <https://bit.ly/3w9geLU>

Food is for Life and Nourishment!

Nutrition Education Module 1

Learning objectives:

1. Describe the role of food as nourishment and essential element in sustaining life;
2. Understand the basic food groups and its relation to daily diet; and
3. Learn how to use Pingang Pinoy for proper nutrition.

Everybody needs to eat certain amount of food to sustain life. Enjoying variety of colors, texture, flavor, and aroma engages us to eat food to nourish our body to survive, function, and live a quality life.

Good food can come from home-grown crops and can be easily prepared or cooked. Local and sustainable sources of plant-based foods are highly essential to have good nutrition.

Good nutrition is the bedrock of child survival, health, and development. Well-nourished children are better able to grow and learn, to participate in and contribute to their communities, and to be resilient in the face of disease, disasters, and other global crises (UNICEF).

Our body obtains fuel or energy from the food we eat. It is essential to eat a nourishing and well-balanced diet because our bodies depend on it.

Page 1 of 4: Food is for Life and Nourishment!

ICRC CRED IIRR

FOOD IS FOR LIFE AND NOURISHMENT! NUTRITION EDUCATION MODULE 1

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-02-14

Link: <https://bit.ly/3q3y1C8>

Grow Veggies in Your Home Garden!

Nutrition Education Module 2

Learning Objectives:

1. Describe the ideal location in selecting sites for growing vegetables;
2. Discuss different cultural practices and innovations in home gardening; and
3. Apply techniques of harvesting, processing and marketing home garden products

Diverse gardens at home can ensure households of continuous access to fresh, safe and nutritious vegetables. Vegetables are good sources of micronutrients. Micronutrient deficiencies are a serious nutritional problem that affects poor households in the Philippines.

There are many factors that make gardening challenging for many people. These factors include poor soil quality, lack of access to seeds, poor water source, pests and climate related challenges.

Soil productivity condition is important in choosing a site for home gardening.

While BITG can be established in every vacant lots, there are some ideal conditions that must be considered to sustain and maximize its productivity:

1. Good source of water especially during dry months/duration
2. A well drained area to allow excess water flow out easily during rainy season.
3. Relatively fertile soil for plants to grow
4. Sufficient sunshine can penetrate the area
5. Good air circulation

Bio-intensive Gardening Technology (BITG) offers practices and principles that are appropriate for resource poor families. It utilizes locally available materials to sustain soil productivity and also responds to climate change issues.

Page 1 of 8: Start a Home Garden: Grow Your Veggies!

ICRC CRED IIRR

GROW VEGGIES IN YOUR HOME GARDEN! NUTRITION EDUCATION MODULE 2

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-02-14

Link: <https://bit.ly/3nTGF4z>

Food Safety is Linked to Nutrition

Nutrition Education Module 3

Learning Objectives:

1. Discuss the importance of food safety;
2. Apply proper food safety practices by:
 - ✓ Learning to identify and classify the risks and hazards to food safety;
 - ✓ Understanding the fundamentals to prevent food borne illness and food contamination;
 - ✓ Learning the various factors affecting microbial growth; and
 - ✓ Guiding food handlers and children the importance of food safety and hygiene.

From garden to plate make food safe: reduce food hazards, prevent food spoilage, prevent contamination, prevent food borne illness with frequent handwashing, and practice good personal hygiene.

Page 1 of 11: Food Safety is Linked to Nutrition

ICRC CRED IIRR

FOOD SAFETY IS LINKED TO NUTRITION NUTRITION EDUCATION MODULE 3

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-02-14

Link: <https://bit.ly/3mEM3Jg>

Good Hygiene Practices Help Fight Sickness and Malnutrition

Nutrition Education Module 4

Learning Objectives:

1. Discuss the importance of personal hygiene to health.
2. Enumerate the basic personal hygiene practices; and
3. Identify three (3) types of worms and its prevention.

Poor hygiene is the most common cause of diarrhea and intestinal worm infection.

Handwashing with soap is very cost-effective to fight sickness and malnutrition.

Benefits of good personal hygiene:

1. Promotes good health
2. Helps feel good
3. Maintains a healthy smile
4. Helps maintain strong and healthy gums
5. Minimizes the risk of infection
6. Prevents the spread of bacteria and viruses

Proper grooming and healthy personal habits help ward off illnesses and make a person feel good. Make it a habit!

Health is a spectrum of good practices. One of these is good personal hygiene, which is essential to promote health.

Page 1 of 6: Good Hygiene Practices Help Fight Sickness and Malnutrition

GOOD HYGIENE PRACTICES HELP FIGHT SICKNESS AND MALNUTRITION

NUTRITION EDUCATION MODULE 4

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-02-14

Link: <https://bit.ly/3BHEoQr>

Simple Physical Activities for Healthy Mind and Body

Nutrition Education Module 5

Learning objectives:

1. Understand the importance of physical activity and exercise for optimum health.
2. Be able to encourage children to engage in physical activities and exercises;
3. Be able to differentiate exercise and physical activity;
4. Appreciate the benefits of physical activity and exercise; and
5. Learn suggested physical activities and exercises for school-age children.

Exercise is integral in achieving overall health. When partnered with proper nutrition, optimum well-being is highly attainable.

Quick Facts

In the 2013 National Nutrition Survey of the Food and Nutrition Research Institute (FNRI-DCST), 3 out of 10 Filipino adults are overweight or obese, a very high prevalence of physical inactivity was found among adults. Globally, physical inactivity has also been identified as the fourth leading risk factor for mortality, causing an estimated 3.2 million deaths (WHO).

Act now!

Teach your young school children the importance of physical activity. Introducing them to its benefits and roles on health can make an impact on their daily habits as early as now. And if paired with proper nutrition, children can achieve optimal health and development.

In the current era of digital devices, encouraging children to engage in physical activities is as difficult as influencing them to eat their vegetables and fruits. They are increasingly exposed to hand-held devices causing them to develop habits with very minimal physical activity. It's now more challenging to invite them to outdoor activities like gardening or to the different fun things like we have such as playgrounds.

Page 1 of 4: Simple Physical Activities for Healthy Mind and Body

SIMPLE PHYSICAL ACTIVITIES FOR HEALTHY MIND AND BODY

NUTRITION EDUCATION MODULE 5

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-02-14

Link: <https://bit.ly/3byFWQF>

Feeding Babies Aged 0-6 months: Exclusive Breastfeeding

Breast milk is the only food a baby needs during the first six months

- It makes the baby grow strong and healthy.
- Breast milk gives babies all the food and water they need during the first six months of life.
- A baby's stomach cannot digest any foods except breast milk.
- Exclusive breastfeeding until the baby is six months old protects the baby against illnesses. Exclusive breastfeeding means giving the baby breast milk only and nothing else.

Feed your baby only breast milk during the first 6 months

- Put the baby to your breast immediately after birth. A new-born baby can suckle (feed) strongly.
- Give the first milk (colostrum) to your baby. It protects her/him from many diseases.
- Your breast milk has all the food and water your baby needs. Do not give any other water or foods in the first 6 months. It could make your baby sick. (Easier with diarrhea).
- Breastfeed when the baby wants to feed, at least 8-10 times during the day and night.
- Regular breastfeeding will help your body to produce enough milk and keep your breasts from becoming swollen and painful.
- Never practice mixed feeding (which means combining breastfeeding with infant formula or other foods).
- Discuss with your health care centre which feeding method is suitable for your baby.

Breastfeeding your baby:

- Start breastfeeding immediately after birth and do not give any other food or drink.
- Immediately go to the clinic if you have cracked nipples or sore breasts, or if your baby has sores or bluish in the mouth.
- After six months stop breastfeeding quickly (e.g. over 2 days to 3 weeks maximum).

Page 1 of 2: Feeding Babies Aged 0-6 months: Exclusive Breastfeeding

FEEDING BABIES AGED 0-6 MONTHS: EXCLUSIVE BREASTFEEDING

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-02-14

Link: <https://bit.ly/2YfknBA>

Grow Healthy and Smart with Iodine

Iodine is important because:

- It makes the brain and body function properly.
- It is essential to the healthy development of unborn babies and young children.
- It helps pregnant women deliver healthy babies.

Everybody needs iodine!

Sources of Iodine:

- Fish
- Seafoods
- Seaweeds
- Iodized Salt

In areas where it is hard to get seafood and seafood, iodized salt is an important part of every diet.

Lack of iodine results in:

- Poor school performance in children
- Mental retardation
- Impaired mental and physical development of the child during pregnancy (cretinism)
- Gobiter

Everybody needs enough iodine in their diet to stay healthy and prevent gobiter. Pregnant women and breastfeeding women, and young children need enough iodine to make sure the child develops well, mentally and physically. Iodine helps regulate nerve and muscle function, body temperature, growth, reproduction, and other body functions.

ICDC CCRV IIRR

GROW HEALTHY AND SMART WITH IODINE

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-02-14

Link: <https://bit.ly/3bAabqf>

Stronger Bodies with Iron

Iron makes our bodies strong!

- Strengthens blood
- Builds muscles and brain
- Helps body to work properly

Well-balanced diet provides enough iron.

Sources of Iron:

- Legumes: beans, peas, lentils
- Dark green leafy vegetables: aulofs, natunum, malunggay, pechay, suloyot, kamote tops
- Liver, blood and other organ meat
- Red meat
- Eggs
- Whole grain cereals: adlai, purple glutinous rice, brown rice

Iron from animal foods can be easily used by the body.

Lack of iron results in:

- Iron deficiency anemia
- Reduced physical capacity
- General weakness
- Reduced alertness and concentration
- Pale complexion
- Poor resistance to cold temperatures

Iron from plant-based foods is best eaten with animal-based foods or fruits.

Good fruits to eat with iron-rich plant foods are: avocados, guineas, mangoes, guava, kamote and other local fruits rich in vitamin C

ICDC CCRV IIRR

STRONGER BODIES WITH IRON

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-02-14

Link: <https://bit.ly/3B1hlc>

Healthier Bodies with Vitamin A

We need Vitamin A because:

- Protects against illness
- Helps body to recover more quickly from illness
- Promotes eye health for good vision
- Helps to keep the skin, gut, hair and lungs healthy.

Vitamin A can be found in variety of plant and animal-based foods.

Foods for recommended daily Vitamin A intake:

- 3 medium pieces (or 1/2 cup) of boiled orange tomato can provide 100% of recommended daily intake of Vitamin A for children (6-12 years old) and almost 80% for adults (13 years old and above).
- 1 cup of kababosa (boiled) can give children (6-9 years old) 25 % of their daily recommended Vitamin A intake.
- 1 cup of boiled leaves of atsayot or bañan can provide more than 100% of the recommended dietary intake for children, teenagers (13-19 years old) and adults (20 years old and above). Nonetheless, the same amount of this food can give males (18-19 years old) almost 80% of recommended daily Vitamin A intake.
- 1 cup of suloyot leaves (boiled) can give more than 100% of the recommended daily Vitamin A intake of children (6-9 years old) and almost 90% for 10-12 year old children.
- 1 serving (1/4 cup) of boiled leafy greens can give children (6-12 years old) more than half of their vitamin A recommended intake.
- 1 slice (1/4 cup) of ripe papaya contains Vitamin A equivalent to 20% of the recommended daily Vitamin A intake of children (6-9 years old).

Sources of Vitamin A:

Orange and yellow vegetables:

- Orange and yellow kamote
- Kababosa
- Carrots

Green leafy vegetables:

- Suloyot, bañan, kamote tops
- Kullin, pechay, sigaytoy
- Kampkong, mustasa, malunggay

Orange and yellow fruits:

- Ripe mangoes, papaya
- Pears, and tomatoes

Animal Sources:

- Liver (chicken, pork, beef)
- Eggs (egg yolk)
- Milk, butter, margarine and cheese

ICDC CCRV IIRR

HEALTHIER BODIES WITH VITAMIN A

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-02-14

Link: <https://bit.ly/3GKFc9j>

ADDRESSING MALNUTRITION THROUGH SCHOOL INTERVENTION

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2016-03-14

Link: <https://bit.ly/3bDuC5O>

INTEGRATED SCHOOL NUTRITION

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-02-09

Link: <https://bit.ly/3wc3HYa>

SECURING THE FUTURE FOR CHILDREN IN THE PHILIPPINES THROUGH SCHOOL NUTRITION INTERVENTION

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2015-07-14

Link: <https://bit.ly/3CNYA32>

CAMBODIA

SCALING OF CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE VIA CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGES IN SOUTHEAST ASIA: INSIGHTS AND LESSONS FROM VIETNAM, LAOS, PHILIPPINES, CAMBODIA AND MYANMAR

Authors: Barbon WJ, Punzalan B, Wassman R, Bui VL, Vidallo R, Villanueva J, Talsma T, Bayot R, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-11

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/115833>

A FINANCIAL ANALYSIS OF HOMESTEAD NATIVE CHICKEN RAISING: A CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE OPTION ADOPTED IN THE PROVINCE OF KOH KONG, CAMBODIA

Authors: Manilay AA, Phen B, Cabriole MA, Thy O, Gonsalves J, Monville-Oro E, Barbon WJ.

Date: 2021-09

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/114901>

COVID-19 IMPACT ON LOCAL AGRI-FOOD SYSTEM IN CAMBODIA, MYANMAR, AND THE PHILIPPINES: FINDINGS FROM A RAPID ASSESSMENT

Authors: Espino A, Itliong K, Ruba CD, Thy O, Barbon WJ, Monville-Oro E, Gummadi S, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-06

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/113843>

LOCAL FOOD SYSTEMS IN CAMBODIA, MYANMAR, AND THE PHILIPPINES: PERSPECTIVE FROM THE LOCAL COMMUNITIES

Authors: Espino, Apple; Monville-Oro, Emily; Barbon, Wilson John; Ruba, Christine Dianne; Gummadi, Sridhar; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2021-05-28

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/113826>

IIRR ENGAGEMENTS IN CAMBODIA: PROJECT SNAPSHOT

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2020-07

Link: <http://bit.ly/3ceOzS1>

ENGAGEMENT OF IIRR IN PROMOTION OF THE AGROFORESTRY SYSTEMS IN THMA BANG DISTRICT, KOH KONG PROVINCE

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction and Cambodian Center for Study and Development in Agriculture

Date: 2019-12

Link: <http://bit.ly/3ilKhmy>

UNLEASHING THE ENTREPRENEURIAL POTENTIAL IN RURAL CAMBODIA: NATIVE CHICKEN PRODUCTION

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction and Cambodian Center for Study and Development in Agriculture

Date: 2019-09

Link: <http://bit.ly/3pkBmKY>

SHARPENING OUR UNDERSTANDING OF FOOD SYSTEMS (English version)

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction and International Center for Tropical Agriculture

Date: 2019-02-27

Link: <http://bit.ly/2M46PCP>

SHARPENING OUR UNDERSTANDING OF FOOD SYSTEMS (Khmer version)

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction and International Center for Tropical Agriculture

Date: 2019-02-27

Link: <http://bit.ly/3c8VqMI>

PROMOTING RESILIENT COMMUNITY FISHERIES IN KOH KONG PROVINCE (PRCF-KK), CAMBODIA: BRIEF

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2018-09

Link: <http://bit.ly/2Y9aGAL>

INDIGENOUS CHICKEN PRIMER (IMPROVED SMALL-SCALE INDIGENOUS CHICKEN RAISING)

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction and Cambodian Center for Study and Development in Agriculture

Date: 2018-08

Link: <http://bit.ly/39czQ88>

BETTER LOCAL WATER GOVERNANCE OF COMMUNITY PONDS: A ROLE FOR WATER USER GROUPS

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction and Cambodian Center for Study and Development in Agriculture

Date: 2018-08

Link: <http://bit.ly/3a5aCYF>

CLIMATE RESILIENT, HIGH VALUE, INTENSIVE VEGETABLE PRODUCTION

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction and Cambodian Center for Study and Development in Agriculture

Date: 2018-03

Link: <http://bit.ly/3iJ3Z1P>

BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION CORRIDORS: PROJECT BRIEF

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction and Cambodian Center for Study and Development in Agriculture

Date: 2018-01

Link: <http://bit.ly/3pstlDC>

SUPPORTING THE TRANSFORMATION OF LIVELIHOODS: VILLAGE DEVELOPMENT FUNDS MANAGED BY SELF-HELP GROUPS

Authors: Gonsalves, Julian; Soria, Giulia; Or, Thy; Yim, Soksophors; Tong, Chantheang; Tath, Sok

Date: 2019-09-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/107805>

INTRODUCING IMPROVED PRACTICE ON NATIVE CHICKEN PRODUCTION TO SMALLHOLDER FARMERS IN MONDULKIRI AND KOH KONG PROVINCES

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction and Cambodian Center for Study and Development in Agriculture

Date: 2019-01-12

Link: <http://bit.ly/3ao4mkD>

ENHANCING THE MANAGEMENT OF FOREST ECOSYSTEM

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction and Cambodian Center for Study and Development in Agriculture

Date: 2018-01-05

Link: <http://bit.ly/3iJEkGk>

HOMESTEAD AGRICULTURE IN DROUGHT & SALINITY AFFECTED AREAS: ADDRESSING CLIMATE RESILIENCE, LIVELIHOODS AND NUTRITION CHALLENGES

Authors: Gonsalves, Julian; Or, Thy; Yim, Soksophors; Tong, Chantheang; Vitou, Sam

Date: 2018-01-01

Link: <http://bit.ly/36ra3aD>

CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURE (CSA) TECHNOLOGY PORTFOLIOS FOR RICE-BASED SYSTEMS: (SALINE, UPLAND, AND LOWLAND ECOSYSTEMS)

Authors: Gonsalves, Julian; Or, Thy; Yim, Soksophors; Tong, Chantheang

Date: 2018-01-01

Link: <http://bit.ly/3iJJO3N>

CONSERVATION CORRIDORS: HOW LOCAL-LIVELIHOOD ENHANCEMENT CAN CONTRIBUTE (STORIES OF CHANGE IN COMMUNITIES WITHIN FOREST ECOSYSTEMS IN CAMBODIA)

Authors: Thy, O., Chantheang, T., Soksophors, Y., Vath, V., Kol, S, Julian, G.

Date: 2020-05

Link: <http://bit.ly/3sT4cUX>

HOMESTEADS AND FAMILY FARMS: EFFECTIVE NICHES AND PLATFORMS FOR BIODIVERSITY-RICH, NATURE-FRIENDLY AGROECOLOGICAL AGRICULTURE

Authors: IIRR and CEDAC
 Date: 2021-08
 Link: <https://bit.ly/2X3DsGf>

RESTORING PRODUCTIVITY IN DROUGHT AND SALINE-AFFECTED RICE GROWING AREAS: CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION IN AGRICULTURE

Authors: IIRR and CEDAC
 Date: 2021-08
 Link: <https://bit.ly/3yR6SnZ>

LOCAL FINANCING MECHANISMS: SUPPORTING COMMUNITY-LEVEL INVESTMENTS IN LOCAL ADAPTATION

Authors: IIRR and CEDAC
 Date: 2021-07
 Link: <https://bit.ly/3BR2J51>

SMALL LIVESTOCK: CLIMATE-SMART, ENVIRONMENTALLY SOUND, ECONOMICALLY EMPOWERING, GENDER-FAIR AND TRANSFORMATIVE AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES IN CAMBODIA

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction; Cambodian Center for Study and Development in Agriculture

Date: 2020-12-21

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/111538>

RESILIENCE BUILDING AGAINST CLIMATE RISKS AND IMPACTS AT LOCAL AND COMMUNITY LEVELS: A ROLE FOR LOCAL FINANCING MECHANISMS

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction; Cambodian Center for Study and Development in Agriculture

Date: 2020-12-21

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/111540>

ECOSYSTEMS-BASED ADAPTATION IN THE FOREST AND AGRICULTURE INTERFACE: OPERATIONALIZING ACTION IN MONDULKIRI AND KOH KONG

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction; Cambodian Center for Study and Development in Agriculture

Date: 2020-12-21

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/111541>

MYANMAR

NURTURING ADAPTATION CAPACITIES IN CHIN HIGHLANDS. LESSONS FROM SAKTA: A CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGE IN MYANMAR

Authors: Barbon, Wilson John; Myae, Chan; Su, Myat Noe; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2020-12

Link: <http://bit.ly/3hFpG2s>

PROMOTING NUTRITION IN CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURE

Authors: Itliong, Kirstein; Valdemoro, Camille; Calica, Michelle Jeanne; Barbon, Wilson John; Myae, Chan; Su, Myat Noe; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2020-08-21

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/109055>

NUTRITION CO-BENEFITS OF CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE IN MYANMAR

Authors: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction; CGIAR Research Program on Climate Change, Agriculture and Food Security

Date: 2020-01-08

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/107814>

RESOURCE CONSERVATION IN THE UPLANDS OF SOUTHERN SHAN: HOW CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE CAN HELP

Authors: Gonsalves, Julian; Wilson John Barbon; Chan Myae; Yinn Minn Latt

Date: 2018-12-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/99501>

REGENERATING DRYLANDS IN RESPONSE TO A CHANGING CLIMATE

Authors: Gonsalves, Julian; Wilson John Barbon; Chan Myae; Yinn Minn Latt

Date: 2018-12-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/99496>

DIVERSIFICATION: REDUCING RISKS, INCREASING INCOMES WHILE ENHANCING ADAPTIVE CAPACITIES IN THE AYEYARWADY DELTA

Authors: Gonsalves, Julian; Wilson John Barbon; Chan Myae; Yinn Minn Latt

Date: 2018-12-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/99494>

CAPITALIZING ON LOCAL LIVELIHOOD DIVERSITY: ENHANCING RESILIENCE BUILDING OF SMALL HIGHLAND FARMS

Authors: Gonsalves, Julian; Wilson John Barbon; Chan Myae; Yinn Minn Latt

Date: 2018-12-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/99491>

CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURE OPTIONS FOR MYANMAR SMALL-HOLDER FARMERS: EDUCATION AND TRAINING POSTERS FOR VILLAGES

Author: International Institute of Rural Reconstruction

Date: 2020-08-21

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/109054>

INTEGRATING GENDER DIMENSIONS IN THE MYANMAR CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGES

Authors: Dayo H, Barbon WJ, Thant PS, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-11

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/115854>

SCALING OF CLIMATE-SMART AGRICULTURE VIA CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGES IN SOUTHEAST ASIA: INSIGHTS AND LESSONS FROM VIETNAM, LAOS, PHILIPPINES, CAMBODIA AND MYANMAR

Authors: Barbon WJ, Punzalan B, Wassman R, Bui VL, Vidallo R, Villanueva J, Talsma T, Bayot R, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-11

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/115833>

COVID-19 IMPACT ON LOCAL AGRI-FOOD SYSTEM IN CAMBODIA, MYANMAR, AND THE PHILIPPINES: FINDINGS FROM A RAPID ASSESSMENT

Authors: Espino A, Itliong K, Ruba CD, Thy O, Barbon WJ, Monville-Oro E, Gummadi S, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-06

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/113843>

LOCAL FOOD SYSTEMS IN CAMBODIA, MYANMAR, AND THE PHILIPPINES: PERSPECTIVE FROM THE LOCAL COMMUNITIES

Authors: Espino, Apple; Monville-Oro, Emily; Barbon, Wilson John; Ruba, Christine Dianne; Gummadi, Sridhar; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2021-05-28

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/113826>

THE PROMOTION OF CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGES TO SUPPORT COMMUNITY-BASED ADAPTATION PROGRAMMING IN MYANMAR

Authors: Barbon, Wilson J.; Vidallo, Rene; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2017-09-07

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/83372>

FINANCIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS FROM FRUIT TREES IN MYANMAR'S CENTRAL DRY ZONE: CASE STUDY FROM HTEE PU CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGE

Authors: Manilay A, Barbon WJ, Cabriole MA, Myae C, Thant PS, Gummadi S, Monville-Oro E, Gonsalves J.

Date: 2021-07

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/114390>

TRAINING ON ESTABLISHING CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGES (CSVs) IN MYANMAR TO IMPROVE FOOD SECURITY AND RESILIENCE IN AGRICULTURE

Authors: Barbon, Wilson John; Myae, Chan; Bayot, Ruvicyn S.; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2019-06-01

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/107415>

CLIMATE AND NUTRITION-SMART VILLAGES AS PLATFORMS TO ADDRESS FOOD INSECURITY IN MYANMAR: FINAL PROJECT END REPORT

Authors: Barbon, Wilson John, Myae, Chan, Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2021-07-15

Link: <https://bit.ly/3lZwSsR>

BUILDING ADAPTIVE CAPACITIES OF LOCAL COMMUNITIES: STORIES OF CHANGE FROM THE CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGES IN MYANMAR

Authors: Myae C, Lian AV, Khar SN, Myint O, & Barbon WJ

Date: 2021-05

Link: <https://bit.ly/3kJUbrd>

NURTURING RESILIENCE IN SMALLHOLDER FARMING SYSTEMS: EMERGING INSIGHTS FROM A CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGE IN SOUTHERN SHAN STATE, MYANMAR

Authors: Barbon, Wilson John; Myae, Chan; Su, Myat Noe; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2020-07-03

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/108682>

RESTORING DRYLANDS, STRENGTHENING RESILIENCE: INSIGHTS FROM A CLIMATE-SMART VILLAGE IN HTEE PU, NYAUN OO, MYANMAR

Authors: Barbon, Wilson John; Myae, Chan; Su, Myat Noe; Gonsalves, Julian

Date: 2020-07-03

Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/108683>

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